

NOTES

Synthesis and Structural Characteristics of some Zinc(II) Complexes of *N*-Aralkylsalicylaldimine

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WE report in this communication results of our studies on a series of zinc complexes of *N*-aralkylsalicylalimine group of Schiff bases.

Experimental

The ligands B₁ to B₉ (Fig. 1) were prepared by condensing salicylaldehyde or its 3-OCH₃, 3-NO₂ and 5-NO₂ ring substituted derivatives separately with benzyl- and -phenylethyl amines as detailed earlier¹.

B₁; X=H, n=1 B₅; X=6-NO₂, n=1
B₂; X=H, n=2 B₆; X=5-NO₂, n=2
B₃; X=3-OCH₃, n=1 B₇; X=3-NO₂, n=1
B₄; X=3-OCH₃, n=2 B₈; X=3-NO₂, n=2

Fig. 1

Preparation of complexes in presence of base: Anhydrous zinc chloride (1.36 g, 0.01 mol) and ligand (0.02 mol) dissolved separately in ethanol (25 ml each) were mixed together. Sodium hydroxide solution (0.8 g, 0.02 mol, dissolved in 8 ml of water) was then added gradually with stirring. The mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for 10 min and then filtered hot. The resulting solid complexes (sl. nos. 1-7, Table 1) were recrystallised from ethanol.

Preparation of complexes in absence of a base: Requisite quantities of anhydrous zinc chloride (0.01 mol) and ligand (0.02 mol) were dissolved in dry methanol (25 ml) and dry benzene (25 ml), respectively. The two solutions were mixed rapidly and stirred vigorously for 10 min and then left the reaction mixture undisturbed. The resulting yellow solid complexes (sl. nos. 8-10, Table 1) were filtered, washed 2-3 times with dry ethanol and dried in a vacuum desiccator over fused calcium chloride. No attempt was made to purify them further. Compounds sl. nos. 1-4 were colourless white-needles, 5-7 light yellow powder and 8-10 yellow granules or plates.

Conductivity measurements were made at room temperature using a Toshniwal conductivity meter. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer S-77 spectrophotometer, and far-infrared spectra were recorded in nujol using CsI windows. Pmr spectra of some of the complexes were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrometer using TMS and deuterated chloroform as the reference standard and solvent, respectively. Analytical and physical data are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF ZINC(II) COMPLEXES

Sl. no.	Compd.*	M.p. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			Λ _M ** × 10 ³ Ω ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹
			N	Zn	OI	
1.	Bis(<i>N</i> -benzyl-SAL)Zn	185	5.42 (5.77)	12.88 (13.47)	—	48.5 ^a
2.	Bis(<i>N</i> -phenylethyl-SAL)Zn	172-3	5.40 (5.47)	12.65 (12.79)	—	51.5 ^a
3.	Bis(<i>N</i> -benzyl-3-methoxy-SAL)Zn	202	5.01 (5.18)	11.68 (11.68)	—	54.5 ^a
4.	Bis(<i>N</i> -phenylethyl-3-methoxy-SAL)Zn	192	5.20 (4.88)	11.16 (11.45)	—	114.6 ^a
5.	Bis(<i>N</i> -benzyl-5-nitro-SAL)Zn	305-7	10.04 (9.73)	10.97 (11.39)	—	57.5 ^a
6.	Bis(<i>N</i> -phenylethyl-5-nitro-SAL)Zn	285-7	9.61 (9.27)	10.40 (10.84)	—	30.1 ^a
7.	Bis(<i>N</i> -benzyl-3-nitro-SAL)Zn	233	9.27 (9.73)	11.12 (11.30)	—	115.0 ^a
8.	Dichlorobis(<i>N</i> -benzyl-SAL)Zn	160	5.24 (5.01)	11.46 (11.71)	12.27 (12.71)	424 ^b
9.	Dichlorobis(<i>N</i> -phenylethyl-SAL)Zn	166	5.05 (4.77)	10.76 (11.15)	12.17 (12.11)	343 ^b
10.	Dichlorobis(<i>N</i> -benzyl-3-methoxy-SAL)Zn	152	4.55 (4.53)	10.28 (10.57)	11.87 (11.48)	260 ^b

*SAL=Salicylalimine or salicylalimine. **In solvent: ^achloroform, ^bnitrobenzene.

Results and Discussion

The complexes sl. nos. 1–7 (Table 1) have 1 : 2 (metal–ligand) stoichiometry. The base seems to facilitate deprotonation of the phenolic group and consequent formation of Zn–O bond. Extremely low values of molar conductances Λ_M indicate non-ionic nature. The broad ir band at 3 100–2 700 cm^{-1} (OH phenolic) for the free ligands, are absent in the spectra of the complexes sl. nos. 1–7 suggesting coordination of phenolic oxygen to Zn^{II} with loss of the phenolic proton. A marginal (10 cm^{-1}) downward displacement of the $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ of the ligands (1 630–1 610 cm^{-1}) in the complexes indicated $\text{C}=\text{N} \rightarrow \text{Zn}$ bond formation³. The 500–490 and 425–380 cm^{-1} bands were assigned to Z–O and Z–N modes, respectively^{3,4}.

The broad pmr signal of the free ligands at δ 12.7–14 (intramolecularly H-bonded phenolic groups) was absent in the spectra of the complexes sl. nos. 1 and 2, thus confirming the deprotonation of the phenolic groups on complex formation. Other signals observed were as expected. However, the signal for the proton attached to the aldehydic carbon displayed a marginal up-field shift, contrary to the expectation. The magnitude of this displacement was found to be δ 0.28 and 0.12 in case of bis(*N*-benzylsalicylaldimine) zinc(II) and its *N*-phenylethyl counterpart, respectively. Theoretically a down-field shift is more likely due to deshielding that occurs in consequence of drainage of electrons from azomethine nitrogen atom while bonding ($\text{C}=\text{N} \rightarrow \text{Zn}$) to the central metal atom. However, the observed behaviour remains unexplained at present.

The complexes sl. nos. 8–10 in absence of a base were well-defined compounds (Table 1). Analytical data of the complexes are consistent with the composition $\text{ZnCl}_2 \cdot (\text{LH})_2$, where LH = Schiff base ligand molecule. A fourth complex was obtained from the sticky mass and could not be properly investigated. Two possible structures can be envisaged for these compounds. Extremely low values of molar conductances in nitrobenzene apparently suggests the formation of $[(\text{LH})_2\text{ZnCl}_2]$ and rules out the possibility of $[(\text{LH})_2\text{Zn}]^{2+}\text{Cl}_2^-$. In methanol solution, conductance value increased with time and reached a limiting value within 24 h at room temperature. This can satisfactorily be explained presuming the release of chloride ions,

Attempts to prepare $\text{Zn}(\text{LH})_2\text{Cl}_2$ complexes with Schiff bases derived from 3- NO_2 - and 5- NO_2 -salicylaldehydes did not succeed presumably due to the presence of strong electron-withdrawing nitro group rendering the phenolic group acidic to the extent that they ionise completely even in absence of a base.

The ir spectra of complexes sl. nos. 8–10 show the presence of a broad ν_{OH} band extending over the region 3 250–2 500 cm^{-1} indicating thereby the presence of phenolic-OH group in these complexes. The up-field shift of $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ by about 10 cm^{-1} with complexes sl. nos. 8–10 were attributed to the breakdown of H-bonded ($\text{C}=\text{N} \cdot \text{H}-\text{O}$) structure in the ligand on complex formation. The bands around 470 and 450–415 cm^{-1} were tentatively assigned to $\nu_{\text{Zn}-\text{O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{Zn}-\text{N}}$ modes. The $\nu_{\text{Zn}-\text{Cl}}$ bands expected below 300 cm^{-1} could not be recorded due to limitations of the instrument.

In the pmr spectra slight down-field shift of the signal for the proton attached to the aldehydic carbon atom further supported the coordination of the azomethine group to Zn^{II} . Signals corresponding to the phenolic protons were considerably displaced ($\delta > 1$) down-field in δ 11.6–12.6 region, supporting the conjecture that the phenolic group is only weakly coordinated in these compounds.

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Synthetic and Biocidal Studies of some Bivalent Metal Complexes of Benzaldehyde-salicyloylhydrazones

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WE describe here the complexes of bivalent Co, Ni, Cu and Zn with benzaldehyde-salicyloylhydrazone (BSH or HL). The complexes were characterised by elemental, magnetic, conductance and ir and electron spectral data. Biocidal activity of the metal chelates on fungi *Aspergillus niger* and *A. nidulans* at 37° in agar agar culture media was found to be several folds higher than that of BSH.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. The ligand (BSH) was synthesised¹ by condensing salicylhydrazide with benzaldehyde in equimolar amounts, and the resulting solid was recrystallised from ethanol (70%). The metal complexes were synthesised by reported procedure². The purity of the compounds was tested by tlc. Elemental analysis

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